

PROJECTION OF DEMOGRAPHIC TRENDS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN BUSINESS LANDSCAPE ACROSS THE SECONDARY, TERTIARY, AND QUATERNARY SECTORS

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Abstract

The demographic landscape of active enterprises in the Romanian population holds significant potential for the overall economic development of both the country and Europe at large. The presented data indicates a positive improvement in the business demography of Romania, particularly in the context of increased employment opportunities within newly established enterprises. This paper aims to provide a forecast for the demographic trends in mountain businesses, specifically focusing on the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors. The analysis encompasses projections that contribute to understanding the evolving dynamics of the business landscape in the mountainous regions.

Keywords: mountain business demography, population of active enterprise, forecast

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The imperative for equitable development, aiming to mitigate regional disparities and support less developed countries, was acknowledged in the preamble of the Treaty of Rome in 1957. This treaty also emphasized the promotion of employment and enhanced labor mobility within the Community. A scrutiny of Romania's key macroeconomic indicators reveals that, more than a decade post its EU accession, the country has experienced both the reduction and exacerbation of existing disparities. (Ceaulescu, 2018)

Eurostat data on business demography in mountain entrepreneurship in Romania (excluding agricultural businesses) over the period 2008-2018, particularly in the context of forecasts, manifests variations, prompting a comprehensive analysis. This forecast analysis, coupled with self-correlation analysis, identifies similarities in forecasted observations contingent upon statistical analysis gaps (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-e).

The prognosticated values for the active enterprise population in secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sub-sectors indicate a significant investment focus on the mountainous regions of Romania. Whether through non-reimbursable/reimbursable funds or self-financing mechanisms, the trajectory of mountain entrepreneurship is anticipated to flourish predominantly in the tertiary and quaternary sectors, aligned with the primary sector.

Table 1. The structure of business demography from Romanian mountain for secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors

Year/Indices	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9	I10	I11	I12
2008	166.823	23.926	16.986	16.011	1.265	1.284.229	1.249.353	51.825	43.389	35.560	27.792	74.616
2009	161.131	14.248	28.955	13.181	553	1.130.471	1.096.497	31.967	25.891	49.922	38.769	55.042
2010	144.988	11.498		13.256	832	1.065.478	1.035.313	37.398	32.659			50.873
2011	223.436	27.931	37.692	16.757	251	1.193.044	1.088.489	51.089	33.603	45.430	13.362	52.028
2012	242.464	28.438	14.128	16.396	414	1.234.239	1.108.817	58.065	39.843	30.047	23.484	45.906
2013	246.416	54.785	39.386	13.183	433	1.228.381	1.094.456	83.114	35.159	45.955	13.165	49.956
2014	249.931	23.355	18.864	14.535	417	1.235.524	1.091.701	47.799	34.361	26.850	18.491	41.409
2015	250.856	28.613	21.223	15.179	427	1.237.507	1.093.175	48.456	29.903	29.036	12.862	47.392
2016	259.915	26.915	21.307	25.925	499	1.333.250	1.149.066	45.747	27.422	28.178	12.509	69.618
2017	268.422	30.330	20.587	14.042	472	1.343.469	1.170.353	49.122	31.191	34.212	16.786	50.805
2018	275.467	30.652		18.573	413	1.328.165	1.182.500	47.938	30.020			50.105
2018/2008	65,1	28,1	21,2	16,0	-67,4	3,4	-5,4	-7,5	-30,8	-3,8	-39,6	-32,8

Year/Indices	I13	I14	I15	I16	I17	I18	I19	I20	I21	I22	I23	I24	I25	I26	I27

2008	41.322		24,52	14,34	10,18		9,6	4,04	2,17	83,72	2,77	2,09	80,57	5,81	
2009	35.724	-3,41	26,81	8,84	17,97		8,18	2,83	2,24	80,99	4,42	1,72	54,08	4,87	
2010	34.287	-10,02		7,93			9,14	3,51	3,25	87,33			48,37	4,77	
2011	34.889	54,11	29,37	12,5	16,87	70,04	7,5	4,28	1,83	65,77	3,81	1,21	49,12	4,36	1,46
2012	28.577	8,52	17,56	11,73	5,83	115,08	6,76	4,7	2,04	68,62	2,43	2,13	60,64	3,72	2,39
2013	33.282	1,63	38,22	22,23	15,98	114,65	5,35	6,77	1,52	42,3	3,74	1,17	50,1	4,07	2,52
2014	29.112	1,43	16,89	9,34	7,55	52,04	5,82	3,87	2,05	71,89	2,17	1,42	42,24	3,35	2,46
2015	29.683	0,37	19,87	11,41	8,46	53,38	6,05	3,92	1,69	61,71	2,35	1,37	59,66	3,83	2,52
2016	43.839	3,61	18,55	10,36	8,2	47,32	9,97	3,43	1,7	59,94	2,11	1,32	58,8	5,22	2,87
2017	32.222	3,27	18,97	11,3	7,67	60,12	5,23	3,66	1,62	63,5	2,55	1,66	57,67	3,78	2,72
2018	33.703	2,62		11,13		64,91	6,74	3,61	1,56	62,62			48,67	3,77	2,37
2018/2008	-18,4	-176,8	-22,6	-22,4	-24,7	-7,3	-	-	-28,1	-25,2	-7,9	-20,6	-39,6	-	62,3
							29,8	10,6						35,1	

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

Evident in Figures 1 (Predictions for Romania's mountain entrepreneurship in 2028 across discussed sectors) and 2 (Forecasts for mountain entrepreneurship regarding the residual autocorrelation function), the sub-sectors poised for substantial development in Romania encompass Industry (excluding construction), Constructions, Transport and storage, Arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities, Accommodation and food services, Information and communication, Financial and insurance activities, and real estate activities (excluding companies). Specifically, these sectors are anticipated to experience lucrative growth. The imperative role of Romanian public governance lies in supporting these sectors, considering them as a foundational support crucial for the coexistence of others.

Observably, the forecasted scenarios exhibit minimal error deviation concerning both the upper and lower control limits. This validates the accuracy of the statistical and forecast analysis.

Indicators considered in the study:

1. Active business population - number (I1)
2. Newly established businesses - number (I2)
3. Abolition of businesses in t - number (I3)
4. Newly established enterprises in t-3 that have survived to t - number (I4)
5. Enterprises with high employment growth (increase of 10% or more) - number (I5)
6. Persons employed in enterprises active in t - number (I6)
7. Employed in enterprises active in t - number (I7)
8. Persons engaged in business established in t - number (I8)
9. Employees in businesses established in t - number (I9)
10. Persons engaged in business abolished in t - number (I10)
11. Employees in businesses dissolved in t - number (I11)
12. Persons employed in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I12)
13. Persons employed in the year of establishment in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I13)
14. Net business growth - percentage (I14)
15. Net business situation: establishment rate + dissolution rate - percentage (I15)

16. Establishment rate: number of enterprises established in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I16)
17. Dissolution rate: number of enterprises disbanded in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I17)
18. 3-year survival rate: number of enterprises in the reference period (t) newly established in t-3 that survived to t divided by the number of enterprises established in t-3 - percentage (I18)
19. Share of enterprises aged 3 years in the business population - percentage (I19)
20. Employment rate of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in the total number of active enterprises - percentage (I20)
21. Average size of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of start-ups in t (I21)
22. Rate of new employees paid in enterprises: number of employees in the reference period (t) of newly established enterprises in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises newly established in t - percentage (I22)
23. Employment rate in disbanded enterprises: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) within the disbanded enterprises divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises active in t - percentage (I23)

24. Enterprise growth rate of three years: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) in newly established enterprises in t-3, which survived to t, divided by the number of persons employed in t -3 by the same companies, a percentage growth rate - percentage (I24)

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25. Employment rate of enterprises older than 3 years: number of persons employed in newly established enterprises in t-3 who survived in t, divided by the number of persons employed in active enterprises - percentage (I25)

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26. Share of high-growth enterprises in employment: number of high-growth enterprises divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I26)

27. Share of enterprises with measured increased growth in employment: number of enterprises with increased growth divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I27).

Sectors covered in the study:

- Industry, construction, and services, except for insurance activities of companies (Ix);
- Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (Ix1);
- Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities (Ix2);
- Industry (except construction) (Ix3);

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- Constructions (Ix4);
- Transport and storage (Ix5);
- Arts, entertainment and recreation; other service activities (Ix6);
- Accommodation and food services (Ix7);
- Information and communication (Ix8);
- Education, human health and social assistance (Ix9);
- Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, except companies (Ix10).

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